

Multiphysics Modeling of Frontal Polymerization-based Manufacturing of Woven Composites

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Frontal Polymerization (FP)

Frontal ring-opening metathesis polymerization (**FROMP**) of dicyclopentadiene (**DCPD**)

10 cm

- Self-sustaining polymerization front
- Rapid, energy-efficient curing of thermosets

➤ Composite manufacturing

5 cm

1 cm

Motivation: FP-based Composite Additive Manufacturing

Reactive Extrusion of CFRP Tows

- Heated rollers consolidate and supply thermal energy to cure unidirectional tow

$$V_f \sim 0.3 - 0.4$$

Hmeidat et al., 2024

Rapid Out-of-oven Lamination

- High throughput lamination for rapid curing of composite beams and panels

$$V_f \sim 0.6$$

Abdullah et al., 2025

Reactive Extrusion of Woven Composite Tubes

- Self-sustaining front propagates longitudinally through extruded tube

$$V_f \sim 0.4 - 0.5$$

Hmeidat et al. 2024

Additive Manufacturing of Composites via In-Situ Curing

Dojan et al., 2025

Overview

- Develop framework to predict front speed during FP in various composite architectures, using computational tools and homogenized analytical models

Composite laminates

Woven composites

Composite Structures
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Multiscale modeling of frontal polymerization in laminated and woven composites

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Thermo-Chemical Model for Composite Curing

Microscale

$\sim 10 \mu m$

Mesoscale

$\sim 1 mm$

Macroscale

$> 1 cm$

Mesoscale Homogenized Model

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \overline{\rho C_p} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (\overline{\kappa} \cdot \nabla T) + \rho_r H_r (1 - \phi) \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = A \exp\left(\frac{-E}{RT}\right) g(\alpha) \end{array} \right.$$

Phenomenological cure kinetics model

$$g(\alpha) = (1 - \alpha)^n \alpha^m \frac{1}{1 + \exp[C(\alpha - \alpha_c)]}$$

Homogenized thermal properties

$$[\overline{\kappa}]_p = \begin{bmatrix} \overline{\kappa}_{||} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \overline{\kappa}_{\perp} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \overline{\kappa}_{\perp} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\overline{\kappa}_{||}(\phi) = \kappa_r (1 - \phi) + \kappa_{f1} \phi$$

$$\overline{\kappa}_{\perp}(\phi) = \kappa_r \frac{\kappa_{f2} (1 + \phi) + \kappa_r (1 - \phi)}{\kappa_{f2} (1 - \phi) + \kappa_r (1 + \phi)}$$

$$\overline{\rho C_p}(\phi) = \rho_r C_{pr} (1 - \phi) + \rho_f C_{pf} \phi$$

AS4 Carbon
Fiber properties

κ_{f1}	6.83 W/m-K
κ_{f2}	2.7 W/m-K
C_{pf}	1129 J/kg-K
ρ_f	1790 kg/m ³

Front Speed in Composites

Front speed prediction in unidirectional composite tow

$$V_{f,||} = \sqrt{\max_{\varepsilon} \frac{A \bar{\kappa}_{||} R \tilde{T}(\varepsilon)^2}{\rho_r H_r (1 - \phi) E} \exp\left(-\frac{E}{R \tilde{T}(\varepsilon)}\right) \frac{1}{\bar{\Pi}}}$$

where

$$\tilde{T}(\varepsilon) = T_0 + \frac{\rho_r H_r (1 - \phi)}{\rho C_p} (1 - \alpha_0 - \varepsilon)$$

$$\bar{\Pi}(\varepsilon) = \int_0^{1-\varepsilon-\alpha_0} \frac{y}{g(1-\varepsilon-y)} dy$$

Process parameters and chemistry control front speed:

Chemical composition

Ansatz: In complex 3D composite laminates, we propose the front speed prediction

$$V_f = \sqrt{\bar{\kappa}_{eff}} \cdot \frac{V_{f,||}}{\sqrt{\bar{\kappa}_{||}}}$$

Model for FP in Composite Laminates

Lamina-level thermal conductivity

$$[\bar{\kappa}(\beta_i)] = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\kappa}_{xx} & \bar{\kappa}_{xy} & 0 \\ \bar{\kappa}_{xy} & \bar{\kappa}_{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \bar{\kappa}_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \quad \begin{aligned} \bar{\kappa}_{xx}(\beta_i) &= \bar{\kappa}_{||} \cos^2 \beta_i + \bar{\kappa}_{\perp} \sin^2 \beta_i \\ \bar{\kappa}_{yy}(\beta_i) &= \bar{\kappa}_{||} \sin^2 \beta_i + \bar{\kappa}_{\perp} \cos^2 \beta_i \\ \bar{\kappa}_{xy}(\beta_i) &= (\bar{\kappa}_{||} - \bar{\kappa}_{\perp}) \cos \beta_i \sin \beta_i \\ \bar{\kappa}_{zz}(\beta_i) &= \bar{\kappa}_{\perp} \end{aligned}$$

Classical lamination theory (CLT) – homogenized thermal conductivity in limit of very thin, perfectly bonded laminate

$$\mathbf{A} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \bar{\kappa}(\beta_i)$$

$$\bar{\kappa}_{CLT} = \frac{1}{\mathbf{e}_x \cdot \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{e}_x}$$

Example) Single lamina with orientation angle β

$$\bar{\kappa}_{lam}(\beta) = \frac{\bar{\kappa}_{||} \bar{\kappa}_{\perp}}{\bar{\kappa}_{||} \cos^2 \beta + \bar{\kappa}_{\perp} \sin^2 \beta}$$

FP in Angle-Ply Laminates

Asymmetric [$\pm\beta$] angle ply laminate

CLT homogenized thermal conductivity

$$\bar{\kappa}_{CLT} = \bar{\kappa}_{||} \cos^2 \beta + \bar{\kappa}_{\perp} \sin^2 \beta$$

Front speed vs fiber volume fraction

CLT prediction provides accurate prediction in limit $H/w \rightarrow 0$

Effect of Geometry in Angle-Ply Laminates

$T_0 = 20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
 $\alpha_0 = 0.01$
 $t = 0.25\text{ mm}$
 $\phi = 0.3$

Front speed at different cross-sectional aspect ratios

$$V_f = (V_{f,CLT} - V_{f,lam}) f\left(\beta, \frac{H}{w}\right) + V_{f,lam}$$

Normalized angle-ply front velocity

Logistic function fit: $f = \frac{1}{1 + \left(m \frac{H}{w}\right)^n}$

Front Shape in Angle Ply Laminates

Front inclination angle along width, γ

$T_0 = 20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
 $\alpha_0 = 0.01$
 $t = 0.25 \text{ mm}$
 $\phi = 0.3$

Front speed and front shape are both impacted by boundary effects

FP in Cross-Ply Laminates

N_0 - number of 0° plies

$T_0 = 20^\circ\text{C}$
 $\alpha_0 = 0.01$
 $t = 0.25\text{ mm}$
 $w \gg H$

Normalized longitudinal fiber volume fraction

CLT homogenized thermal conductivity

$$\bar{\kappa}_{CLT} = \frac{N_0}{N} \bar{\kappa}_{||} + \left(1 - \frac{N_0}{N}\right) \bar{\kappa}_{\perp}$$

N_0/N	Layup
1	[0]
0.75	[0/90/0 ₂]
0.5	[0/90]
0.25	[90/0/90 ₂]
0	[90]

Deviation from CLT prediction at intermediate fiber volume fractions

Effect of Thickness in Cross-Ply Laminates

$T_0 = 20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
 $\alpha_0 = 0.01$
 $N_0/N = 0.5$
 $w \gg H$

Non-monotonic thickness dependence due to competing influence of thermal conductivity in each lamina

Effect is reduced at $\phi = 0.5$ but more prone to quenching

Cure-Induced Deformations in Cross-Ply Laminates

- Thermal expansion and cure shrinkage contribute to distortions and residual stresses in composites
- Preliminary model for thermo-chemo-mechanical behavior during FP predicts warpage of cross-ply panel

Computational Model for Woven Composites

Infinite medium of periodically repeating unit cells rotated by angle β

Truncated, periodic computational domain

Plain Weave Unit cell

Thermal conductivity varies with fiber orientation

$$[\bar{\kappa}] = [Q] [\bar{\kappa}]_p [Q]^T$$

$$Q_{ij} = \mathbf{e}_i \cdot \mathbf{e}'_j$$

$$i, j \in \{\hat{x}, \hat{y}, \hat{z}\}$$

Front Propagation in Plain Weave Composites

$T_0 = 20^\circ\text{C}$
 $\alpha_0 = 0.01$
 $d = 3.6\text{ mm}$
 $d_t = 1.71\text{ mm}$
 $t = 0.275\text{ mm}$

Below $\phi \sim 0.35$, front propagation is unsteady, and front speed exceeds homogenization theory

Front Propagation in Plain Weave Composites

Time: 0.00 s

$\phi = 0.3, \beta = 0^\circ$

Time: 0.00 s

$\phi = 0.3, \beta = 45^\circ$

$T_0 = 20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
 $\alpha_0 = 0.01$
 $d = 3.6\text{ mm}$
 $d_t = 1.71\text{ mm}$
 $t = 0.275\text{ mm}$

4x speed

5 mm

Note: Temperature scale does not include local thermal spikes

Maximum Temperature (T_{max}) Contours

$T_0 = 20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ $d = 3.6\text{ mm}$ $t = 0.275\text{ mm}$
 $\alpha_0 = 0.01$ $d_t = 1.71\text{ mm}$

Peak Temperature in Plain Weave Composites

Max temperature along length of composite

Low fiber volume fraction can result in interaction between front and resin-rich regions

Peak temperature vs fiber volume fraction

$$T_{adiab} = T_0 + \frac{\rho_r H_r}{\rho C_p} (1 - \phi) (1 - \alpha_0)$$

Conclusion

- A multiscale modeling approach was developed to predict planar front speeds during frontal polymerization
- Front speed in laminates is affected by stacking sequence, laminate geometry and thermal environment

Angle Ply Laminates

Cross Ply Laminates

Conclusion

- A multiscale modeling approach was developed to predict planar front speeds during frontal polymerization
- Front speed in laminates is affected by stacking sequence, laminate geometry and thermal environment
- Heterogeneous nature of woven composites may cause non-uniform front propagation

Increasing fiber volume fraction

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Thank you!
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